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AGREEMENT and ellipsis

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Abstract: The interest in such diverse topics such as agreement and ellipsis, and their interaction with several components of the language system (syntax, pragmatics, phonology...) has increased in the last decades, as new approaches emerge to enable more precise analyses of the mechanisms underlying agreement relations and elliptical constructions. This special issue gathers a selection of six papers from the *32nd Colloquium on Generative Grammar* and from the *Workshop on Case, Agreement and Ellipsis* immediately following the 32CGG (University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, April 2023) which focus on two main topics: (i) agreement and related notions, such as feature specification (or underspecification) on heads, the nature of ϕ -feature valuation and the agreement mechanism itself, or a case of predicate ellipsis where a clitic appears to participate in agreement licensing; and (ii) *prima facie* elliptical phenomena, such as Right-Node Raising (analysed through the lenses of discourse), an LF-copying approach to ellipsis, where ellipsis in the main clause is licensed by an adverbial clause, and a syntactic approach to symmetric predicates under VP-ellipsis. This introductory paper serves as a state of the art as well as guide for the readers of this special collection and offers an overview of the topics dealt with in each contribution.

Keywords: agreement; case; merge; ellipsis; antecedent identity

1 A window into agreement

Merge is generally considered a fundamental, “non-negotiable” property of human language that hierarchically organizes linguistic objects (making language structure-dependent). In contrast, the question of whether we need computational operations other than Merge for the construction of syntactic objects requires greater discussion. Looking at the pervasiveness of agreement phenomena in natural languages, many defend that one such operation should be posited: *Agree*, which relates *features* of syntactic objects (Chomsky 2000, 2001). These feature-relations find their expression in morphological inflection in highly variable, language-specific ways.

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